

BILINGUAL YOUNG CHILDREN'S MENTAL ABILITY AND IT'S FACTORS

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ABSTRACT

This article examines the main features of the intellectual development of children in a bilingual environment. The article analyzes the features of intellectual development and the influence of bilingualism on the intellectual development of children.

Children are excellent at distinguishing between languages if they hear them from birth, but can replace words with similar ones from another language if they are easier to pronounce.

Bilingualism, the ability to speak two languages equally, is most often inherent in children in families where parents speak different languages, and the child is exposed to two language environments from birth. However, bilingualism can also be created artificially if one of the parents communicates with their child in a foreign language for the purpose of learning: in this case, it is important to speak two languages with him from a very early age.

Bilingual people can speak, understand, read and write both languages. Bilingualism can be the result of early bilingual upbringing, where a child grows up in an environment where two languages are used, or acquired later in life, for example, through learning and practicing a second language.

Bilingualism has many benefits. Bilingual people usually have greater flexibility of thinking, better ability to concentrate, and they can more easily adapt to new language and cultural situations. Bilingual education can also help develop cognitive skills, improve memory and the ability to multitask.

To develop and maintain bilingualism, it is important to provide regular practice and contexts in both languages. This can be achieved through family communication, reading books, watching films and communicating with native speakers.

What are the benefits of bilingualism?

Bilingualism, bilingualism, has many advantages and benefits for children and adults. Here are some of them:

Cognitive advantages: Research shows that bilingual people have advantages in cognitive skills. Learning and using two languages requires developing linguistic flexibility, lexical richness, logical thinking, and the ability to switch between languages. These skills can lead to more effective problem solving, better analytical thinking, and increased creative thinking.

Cultural understanding and communication: Bilingualism allows people to immerse themselves in two different cultures and communicate with people who speak different languages. It broadens one's perspective and promotes a better understanding and acceptance of differences in culture, customs and values. Bilingual people can communicate effectively with a wider range of people and connect with people from different cultures.

Professional Opportunities: Bilingual people have advantages in the labor market. Knowing two languages can open doors to more jobs and career opportunities, especially in international organizations and companies. Bilingualism can also improve the ability to adapt to new environments and work with different cultures.

Improved memory and cognitive health: Learning and using two languages requires improved memory, attention and cognitive processes. Some research suggests that bilingual people have higher levels of cognitive reserve, which may help them cope with cognitive decline later in life and prevent the development of some neurological diseases such as Alzheimer's disease.

Personal development: Bilingualism promotes personal development, self-awareness and confidence. The ability to speak two languages can strengthen a sense of identity and belonging to different cultures, as well as develop flexibility of thinking and adaptability to different situations.

Research has confirmed that children who speak two languages have a richer vocabulary, better developed memory and analytical abilities, and it is easier for them to further study other languages and exact sciences. Early learning of a second language promotes the development of the part of the brain responsible for verbal fluency - this effect is especially noticeable if a child begins to learn a second language before the age of five.

Is it true that bilingual children speak later?

Bilingual children often start speaking later than their monolingual peers because their vocabulary in each language is smaller and their communication skills may be poor. As a rule, in a bilingual family, the child speaks his first words at the same age as other children, but further speech development may be slow. According to statistics, speech development delays in bilingualism fall within normal development limits. However, experts note that children in bilingual families often experience general underdevelopment of speech: a violation of grammatical structure, coherent speech, and vocabulary. This may happen because it is difficult for a young child to navigate the rules and regulations of two languages at once.

In fact, most studies show that bilingual children develop linguistically as efficiently as monolingual children. They may begin to produce their first words and phrases in each language with some slight time lag, but overall their language development follows the typical development of monolingual children.

There is some variability in the individual rates of language development in children, regardless of their language status. Some children may start speaking early and others may be slower to develop language, but this depends on many factors such as individual differences, the language environment and the stimulation they receive.

It is important to note that children may temporarily show language mixing or use elements of both languages in their speech. This phenomenon is known as language mixing or code-switching and is a normal part of the language development of bilingual children. However, as they age and develop more advanced skills in each language, they usually become more defined and separate the languages more clearly.

In general, bilingual children do not start speaking later, and their language development depends on many factors, including the language environment and the stimulation and support they receive from their parents and others.

Does a bilingual child have one language as his or her primary language?

A bilingual child may have one language that he or she uses most frequently and most comfortably. This language may be called the primary or preferred language. However, it is important to note that this may vary depending on the language environment the child is in and the role each language plays in their life.

The role of the primary language may be determined by factors such as the home environment, parental communication, or the language in which the child is educated. For example, if the parents speak different languages, the child may consider the language he speaks with his parents at home to be his primary language. However, in school or other social situations, another language may become dominant.

It is important to understand that each bilingual child may have a unique language profile, and the role of the primary language may change over time and in different situations. Some children may be more equitable in their use of both languages and not prioritize one language as their primary language. This depends on each child's individual circumstances and experiences.

It is important to support and encourage the development of both languages in a bilingual child by creating a rich language environment and providing opportunities to practice and use both languages in different contexts.

How can you help your child learn both languages more easily?

Here are some strategies that can help your child learn both languages more easily:

Create a language environment: Provide your child with constant language practice in both languages. Talk to him in both languages, read books, play games and watch cartoons in both languages. Create a language environment where both languages are actively used and valued.

Separate roles and contexts: Try to use each language in specific situations or roles. For example, one parent may speak one language to the child at home, but another language may be used with friends or at school. This will help the child associate each language with specific contexts and increase his confidence in using both languages.

Support language communication: Encourage your child to use both languages, even if he mixes them up or makes mistakes. Support his attempts in both languages and help him correct mistakes, without criticism or pressure. It is important to create a positive atmosphere in which the child feels comfortable and encouraged to speak both languages.

Use a variety of materials and resources: Provide your child with access to books, games, toys, and other materials in both languages. This will help him develop vocabulary and understanding in both languages. Also use language apps and online resources that can be helpful for learning and practicing the language.

Communication with native speakers: Try to provide your child with contact with native speakers of each language. This could be through family, friends, community or cultural events. Regular interaction with native speakers will help your child develop authentic pronunciation, understanding of cultural nuances, and confidence in using the language.

It is important to remember that each child is unique and approaches may vary. Monitor your child's needs and interests and adapt strategies to suit his or her individual needs.

It is best to separate the use of two languages when communicating with a child: for example, speak Russian at home and French on the street, or invite him to speak with each parent in his native language. If both parents speak several languages well, you can separate the languages by day of the week. All these methods will help the child differentiate his knowledge and not mix words and sentences in different languages.

What to do if a child confuses languages?

Children are excellent at distinguishing between languages if they hear them from birth, but can replace words with similar ones from another language if they are easier to pronounce. If you gently correct your child's speech every time he uses a word from another language, or ask again, then by the age of three he will completely abandon "mixed" sentences.

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What to do if a child confuses languages?

If your child is confusing languages, there are several steps you can take:

Be patient: Language confusion is a normal part of the language development of bilingual children. It's important to be patient and not feel too anxious or stressed about it. Language confusion decreases over time as the child develops and develops his or her skills in both languages.

Don't over-correct: While correcting mistakes can be helpful, going overboard and correcting every mistake your child makes can create a negative atmosphere and a lack of confidence in using language. Allow your child to express himself freely, even if he mixes languages, and gradually correct him without tension.

Point out the differences: Help your child recognize the differences between languages by pointing out the features of each language. For example, you might say, "In English we say ' dog

', and in Spanish we say 'perro'." This will help the child become aware of the differences and differences between languages.

Provide additional language practice: If you notice that your child is confusing certain words or expressions, provide additional practice on those specific aspects. Read a book in the language your child is struggling with, or do extra language differentiation exercises.

Seek help from a professional: If you have serious concerns about your child's language confusion or speech development, you may want to see a specialist such as a speech therapist or pediatrician who specializes in language development in children. They can offer additional guidance and support.

It is important to remember that language confusion is temporary and often goes away as the child's language skills develop. With support and understanding, you can help your child become more confident in using both languages.

In conclusion, it should be said that Bilingualism- is an accelerator of a child's cognitive and emotional development. Flexibility of thinking, the ability for linguistic creativity, the development of metalinguistic abilities, the development of analytical skills, the variety of cognitive and communicative strategies used in bilingual children testify in favor of early childhood bilingualism. It is also necessary to take into account that in the modern world, knowledge of several foreign languages gives a great advantage in professional, educational and social activities.

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